

Dela kumene kuli nyumba	Nambala ya Kafukufuku	Nambala ya chizindikiro cha nyumba

CHIKALATA CHA CHILOREZO

MUTU WA KAFUKUFUKU

2a. The epidemiology of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* at a household level in Malawi

Mawu olankhulidwa ndi wotenga nawo mbali wamkulu:

Chonde zungulizani mau oti Inde kapena Ayi pofuna kutsimikiza kuti mwavomereza kapena simukuvomerezana ndi mfundo zili m'munsimu:

- Ndawerenga chikalata cha uthenga kapena andiwerengera chikalatachi. Inde / Ayi
- Ndakhala ndi mwayi wofunsa mafunso ndipo ndine wokhutitsidwa ndi mayankho amene aperekedwa. Inde / Ayi
- Ndikuvomereza kutenga nawo mbali m'kafukufukuyu , koma ndikudziwa kuti ndikhoza kusintha maganizo anga nthawi ina iliyonse. Inde / Ayi
- Ndikuvomereza kupereka chimbudzi changa kuti chikayezedwe at visits 1, 2 and 3 ngati mbali imodzi ya kafukufuku. Inde / Ayi
- Ndikumvetsetsa kuti ulendo wa chiwiri udzakonedwa pakatha mwenzi oyamba ndipo ulendo wachitatu udzakonedwa pakatha miyezi isanu ndi umodzi pambuyo pa ulendo oyambilira

- Ndikuvomereza mosakakamizidwa kulowa nawo mukafukufukuyu. Inde / Ayi
- Ndikuvomereza kuti ngati kachirombo ka *E. coli* kapena ka non-typhoidal *Salmonella* kangapezeke, zoyesa zanga zidzatumizidwa ku UK, Kenya kuti ntchito yoyeza ya ***whole genome sequencing*** ikachitike.

Inde / Ayi

Dzina la wotenga nawo mbali kuchokera m'nyumbayi	Deti	Sayini	Sayini
Mboni yopanda mbali (Ngati mwini wake nyumba akulephera kuwerenga)	Deti	Sayini	Chidindo cha chala
Wogwira ntchito amene akutenga chilorezo	Deti	Sayini	Chidindo cha chala

THE COLLEGE OF MEDICINE
Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome Trust
Clinical Research Programme

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